

Investigating the Impact of Virtual Reality (VR) on Improving Resource Accessibility for Individuals with Disabilities

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of virtual reality (VR) technology on improving resource accessibility for individuals with disabilities. Disabilities encompass physical, mental, and sensory impairments that create barriers to participation in various aspects of life, including education, healthcare, employment, and social engagement. The study identifies different categories of disabilities, such as intellectual disabilities, autism spectrum disorders, hearing and visual impairments, and so on. This study employed a descriptive survey design. The research was conducted in three disabled homes in Enugu State, Nigeria—Bina Foundation for People with Special Needs, Cheshire Disability Home, and St. Joseph's Comprehensive Secondary School Uwani. The study's population consists of 800 individuals, including school librarians, individuals with disabilities, and technology specialists, with a stratified sampling technique used to select a sample of 160 respondents. A structured questionnaire based on a 4-point type Likert scale was used to collect data, and analysis was conducted using percentages, means, standard deviations, and regression analysis at a 0.05 significance level. Findings from this research reveal that VR systems hold transformative potential in breaking accessibility barriers by providing tailored solutions for mobility, sensory, and cognitive challenges. However, the study also identified significant challenges, such as usability issues, lack of integration and so on, which limit VR's adoption. Significant challenges such as technical barriers, design and usability issues, and lack of awareness were identified as limiting VR's widespread adoption. The study recommends greater collaboration between developers, policymakers, and individuals with disabilities to drive user-centered VR innovations, enhance accessibility features, and improve adoption.

Keywords: Disabilities, Individuals, Investigate, Virtual Reality (VR), Resource accessibility

Introduction

Disability is not just a health problem; it is a devastating issue that can render an individual almost nothing in life. Sometimes, the person concerned may not really understand what happened to him/her or rather know how to help and assist himself to come out of it. The finding of Sohrabei and Atashi (2021) opined that disability often occurs both physically and mentally, take for instance a stroke person could be very incapacitated to do things for themselves. As a result of the stroke, people suffer from mobility problems, unable to perform everyday activities such as driving and writing and possibly need the application of virtual reality technology to assist the victim. Disability refers to the inability to perform all or part of the activities of individual or social life due to an inherited or acquired defect, its categorization of is most often based on the symptoms and rarely on the causes, because for many disabilities, the cause is unknown or multiple, ([Smart, 2019](#))

The rapid development of virtual reality (VR) technology has created a unique opportunity to address the challenges faced by individuals with disabilities, by providing interactive, and adaptable environments. [Chandrashekar](#) (2018) inferred that Virtual reality (VR) offers all sorts of wondrous opportunities when it comes to making learning more accessible for peoples with disabilities, which are potential to transform how people with disabilities access resources/information, develop skills, and experience the world. It really explores the intersection of emerging technology and accessibility innovation. Virtual reality (VR) is great by assisting the impaired person to customize and adjust the content to fit their abilities and preferences, which helps with differentiated instruction. It actually has the power to boost learning in many different areas (Alkhawaldeh & Alkhawaldeh, 2023). It has actually demonstrated significant utility in enhancing bodily and mechanical functions, often allowing individuals with disabilities to transcend physical barriers. Deluca, *et al.* (2025) inferred that these interventions harness neuroplasticity, the brain's ability to adapt, by simulating movements that may improve motor coordination and function, where people with disabilities can achieve the greatest possible independence, pursue integrated, competitive employment, and live with dignity within our communities. Similarly, VR environments are being tailored for users with cognitive impairments, providing safe spaces to practice skills such as memory recall, social interaction, and daily task routine and management. In the digital realm, the reliance on technology has exposed significant barriers for disabled individuals. Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) are crucial for creating inclusive digital environments, like screen readers, adjustable font sizes, and audio descriptions are of great need for visually impaired users. Similarly, multimedia content with closed captions or sign language interpretation includes those with hearing impairments in engaging fully.

Different categories of disability

Disabilities are often categorized based on the nature and extent of their impact on individuals' physical, mental, or sensory functioning. Each category reflects specific challenges, such as developmental delays in children up to age nine, or the combined difficulties of deaf-blindness

requiring unique interventions. Hickman, 2023 stressed that these classifications ensure tailored educational plans and accommodations to support individuals effectively, as he has been meeting the lifetime legal needs of children and adults with disabilities, the elderly, and their families.

The categories of disabilities could be seen as follows:

- **Intellectual Disability** manifests itself in the form of basic limitations in daily life functions. These limitations include delays in mental development; making inappropriate responses to the environment; not behaving as required by the age range in cognitive, language. Savita and Sharma (2021) inferred that Intellectual disability (mental retardation) refers to a particular state of functioning that begins prior to age 18, characterized by significant limitations in both intellectual functioning and adaptive behaviour, as represented in conceptual, social, and practical adaptive skills.
- **Down Syndrome:** Down syndrome is the most common chromosomal disorder of all genetic disorders that is caused by an error in cell division that cannot be controlled with any treatment or otherwise.
- **Hearing Impairment:** This can be a situation where there are delays in the development of language and communication skills due to partial or complete loss of hearing sensitivity, as such negatively affect the educational performance and social adaptation of such individual.
- **Visual Impairment:** These are individuals who cannot use their eyesight effectively for learning and probably must need Braille or talking books for reading, because of their visual deficiency.
- **Language and Speech Disorders:** This is mainly on the interruption of message exchange and its deviation from social standards, not having a freely communication in speech with someone or unable to pass vocal message to another individual. Others include: **Autism Spectrum Disorder, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder: ADHD, Cerebral Palsy and Gait Disorders.**

Current innovations in VR systems for individuals with diverse disabilities.

Rehabilitation and Physical Therapy: VR has become a significant tool in physical rehabilitation for individuals recovering from strokes, brain injuries, or mobility impairments. Immersive systems stimulate brain activity and motor skills through realistic simulations of physical activities, improving outcomes in motor recovery and coordination. Dartmouth (2023) states that these future developments could include AI-driven personalized therapy plans, integrating real-time data analytics to optimize rehabilitation routines based on user progress and engagement.

Accessibility for Visual Disabilities: VR technologies now incorporate features like automatic gain control, bold visuals, and adjustable contrast, enabling better visual clarity for individuals with low vision. Rubin (2020) opined that users with conditions like retinitis pigmentosa have reported improved vision in VR environments compared to real life.

Cognitive and Social Skill Development: VR systems are being used to support individuals with cognitive impairments, such as autism spectrum disorders. Controlled environments allow users to practice social interactions and life skills safely. Deluca, et al. (2025) also inferred that Virtual reality environments are being customized to support individuals with cognitive impairments, offering secure settings where they can practice memory recall, improve social interactions, and manage everyday tasks.

Integration of AI for Personalization: The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in VR enhances customization, making experiences more accessible. Dartmouth (2023) states that VR interfaces for users with motor disabilities or translate sign language in real time for individuals with hearing impairments.

Enhanced Educational and Vocational Training: VR environments provide realistic simulations for skill acquisition, enabling users to practice tasks like navigating urban environments or job-related scenarios without risk. The finding of [Saudagar](#) et al. (2024) explained that medical students with disabilities benefit from VR-assisted learning, which offers immersive anatomical models and virtual surgeries. Includes Immersive Entertainment and Recreation.

Virtual reality (VR) technologies that can help overcome accessibility barriers faced by

Mobility and Physical Accessibility: VR environments can simulate experiences for individuals with mobility impairments, allowing them to interact in virtual worlds without physical limitations. Users can explore virtual museums or train for physical tasks in a seated position using adaptive hardware, such as eye-tracking or voice-command systems, to navigate the interface.

Sensory Accessibility: For users with visual impairments, VR systems employ features like high-contrast visuals, audio guidance, and text-to-speech capabilities. Yensathit, et al. (2025) stressed that

technologies enable navigation and interaction with virtual environments in ways that can surpass real-world accessibility.

Cognitive Accessibility: VR creates controlled, immersive environments to support individuals with cognitive disabilities such as autism or ADHD. Catania, et al. (2025) inferred that Virtual Reality (VR) is a transformative technology that has garnered increasing attention in the field of neuroscience, neuropsychology, and cognitive rehabilitation, by immersing individuals in interactive, multisensory environments. Others include Workplace Inclusivity and Healthcare and Rehabilitation.

Challenges that limit the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool for individuals with disability

The adoption of virtual reality (VR) as an accessibility tool for individuals with disabilities is promising but faces several challenges that limit its widespread implementation.

Technical Barriers: Current VR devices can be physically cumbersome and may not accommodate diverse accessibility needs. Yang (2024) opined that many VR systems are not designed to integrate with existing accessibility aids, such as screen readers or adaptive switches, further alienating potential users with sensory or motor impairments

Economic Constraints: Developing and acquiring VR systems can be prohibitively expensive, especially for individuals and institutions. In the finding of [MarkWide](#) (2023), he complained that headsets can be [expensive](#), bulky to ship and store, and are known for being uncomfortable when worn for long periods of time.

Design and Usability Challenges: Many VR experiences fail to include features tailored to users with disabilities, such as adaptive difficulty settings, clear navigation aids, or disability representation in avatars. Williams (2022) concerns more about the user's accessibility of VR devices, which are ever-growing as many users struggle to use the technology.

Awareness and Regulatory Issues: There is a lack of universal accessibility standards for VR systems, leading to inconsistent support for individuals with disabilities across platforms. Droutsas et al. (2025) opined that designing for accessibility is a widely recognized practice which is reinforced by legal directives.

Statement of Problems

Accessibility barriers continue to prevent individuals with disabilities from fully participating in various aspects of societal activities and involvement, including education, employment, healthcare, and social engagement. Despite advancements in assistive technologies, gaps remain in providing equitable and adaptive solutions that cater to the diverse needs of this population. Virtual reality (VR) has emerged as a potential tool to bridge these gaps by offering immersive and customizable environments that simulate real-world interactions for their benefits. However, its effectiveness as an accessibility tool remains underexplored. Khasawneh (2023) opined that with technological tools, individuals diagnosed with hyperactivity disorder frequently demonstrate an impaired ability to promptly adjust to changes in their environment or may manifest delayed responses to said change. Moreso, virtual reality enables the learner to engage in self-expression regarding the material presented, which assists learners to participate actively, exchange ideas and thoughts, and observe the operational mechanisms of the virtual reality environment (Tatale *et al.*, 2019). This study seeks to address these issues by investigating how VR can be improved to enhance resource accessibility for individuals with disabilities. It aims to evaluate current applications, identify gaps, and propose solutions to make VR a practical and inclusive tool for accessibility.

The general purpose of this study is to investigating the impact of Virtual Reality (VR) on improving resource accessibility for individuals with disabilities. The following objectives are stated for the study:

1. Identify different categories of disability.
2. Identify current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems that address the needs of individuals with diverse disabilities.
3. explore how virtual reality technologies can help overcome accessibility barriers faced by individuals with disabilities.
4. Identify the challenges that limit the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool for individuals with disability.

Research Questions

The following research questions were postulated for the study:

1. What are the different categories of disability?
2. What current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems for individuals with diverse disabilities.
3. What ways could virtual reality technologies help overcome accessibility barriers faced by individuals with disabilities.
4. What are the challenges that limit the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool for individuals with disabilities.

Research Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis would be tested

H₀₁: There is a significant difference in perceptions of current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems across statuses of the respondents

H₀₂: There is a significant difference in perceptions of challenges limiting the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool across statuses of the respondents

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was used for the study. The areas of the study are three (3) disabled homes in Enugu geopolitical zone in Enugu State, namely: Bina Foundation for people with special needs, Enugu; Cheshire disability home, Enugu; St. Joseph's Comprehensive Secondary School Uwani, Enugu. All these homes have schools and libraries attached to the schools. School librarians/senior workers; individuals with disability and technology specialists are the respondents for this study, and the population of the study was drawn from there. The population of the study is 800, comprising 500 from Bina foundation, 100 from Cheshire home and 200 from St. Joseph. To select the target respondents for the sample of the study, stratified sampling technique was used in selecting 20% of respondents in each homes/school, which are 100, 20, and 40, respectively, making a total of 160 respondents for the study.

The questionnaire was structured in line with the research questions. The responses to the items of the questionnaire are built in 4 points type Likert rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) Agree (A) Disagree (D) Strongly Disagree (SD) and the weights assigned to each response is SA (4), A (3), D (2), SD (1) respectively. The cut-off point was 2.50 therefore any mean score below 2.50 will be rejected, while any mean score 2.50 and above will be accepted. The data collected were analysed using simple percentage, mean scores and standard deviation. The null hypotheses 1&2 was tested using regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Respondents' demographic characteristics

Status	Frequency	Percent
School librarians/senior workers	80	50.6
Individual with disability	28	17.7

Technology specialists	50	31.6
Total	158	100.0
Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	80	50.6
Female	78	49.4
Total	158	100.0
Age Profile	Frequency	Percent
Below 25 years	30	19.0
25-35 years	15	9.5
36-45 year	50	31.6
Above 45 years	63	39.9
Total	158	100.0

Table 1 provides a summary of the respondents’ demographic characteristics, including job status, gender, and age distribution. The demographic profile indicates that 50.6% of the respondents were school librarians or senior workers, with 17.7% respondents, being individuals with disability, and 31.6% being technology specialists. Gender distribution was nearly balanced, with 50.6% males and 49.4% females. Regarding age, the majority (39.9%) were above 45 years, followed by 31.6% aged 36–45 years. Younger respondents below 25 years and those aged 25–35 years constituted smaller proportions of 19.0% and 9.5%, respectively.

Research Question 1: What are the different categories of disability?

Table 2: Respondents' Agreement with Categories of Disability

Items Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SD*	Des.
Intellectual Disability	10 (6.3)	19 (12.0)	88 (55.7)	41 (25.9)	3.01	0.80	A
Down Syndrome	0 (0.0)	10 (6.3)	52 (32.9)	96 (60.8)	3.54	0.61	SA
Hearing Impairment	9 (5.7)	15 (9.5)	94 (59.5)	40 (25.3)	3.04	0.76	A
Language And Speech Disorders	3 (1.9)	9 (5.7)	39 (24.7)	107 (67.7)	3.58	0.69	SA
Autism Spectrum Disorder	6 (3.8)	20 (12.7)	91 (57.6)	41 (25.9)	3.06	0.73	A
Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder	41 (25.9)	97 (61.4)	13 (8.2)	7 (4.4)	1.91	0.72	D
Cerebral Palsy	51 (32.3)	77 (48.7)	29 (18.4)	1 (0.6)	1.87	0.72	D

Gait Disorders	58 (36.7)	68 (43.0)	26 (16.5)	6 (3.8)	1.87	0.82	D
Overall Mean					2.74	0.73	

Key: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree, SD* Standard Deviation, Des.- Decision

Table 2 indicates respondent’s agreement with statements about different categories of disability. The data indicate that respondents strongly agreed with the classification of down syndrome (mean = 3.54) and language and speech disorders (mean = 3.58) as disabilities. Categories such as Intellectual disability, hearing impairment, and autism spectrum disorder were agreed upon by the respondents, with mean scores of 3.01, 3.04, and 3.06, respectively. However, categories such as Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), cerebral palsy, and gait disorders received lower agreement levels, as reflected by mean scores below 2.0, indicating disagreement with these classifications as disabilities. The overall mean score of 2.74 suggests a general agreement with the listed categories of disability, though variability exists across specific items.

Research Question 2: What current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems for individuals with diverse disabilities?

Table 3: Respondents' Perceptions of VR System Advancements and potential Innovations

Items Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SD*	Des.
Rehabilitation and Physical Therapy	0 (0.0)	9 (5.7)	43 (27.2)	106 (67.1)	3.61	0.59	SA
Accessibility for Visual Disabilities	0 (0.0)	5 (3.2)	115 (72.8)	38 (24.1)	3.21	0.48	A
Cognitive and Social Skill Development	38 (24.1)	95 (60.1)	23 (14.6)	2 (1.3)	1.93	0.66	S
Integration of AI for Personalization	4 (2.5)	16 (10.1)	99 (62.7)	39 (24.7)	3.09	0.67	A
Enhanced Educational and Vocational Training	1 (0.6)	3 (1.9)	103 (65.2)	51 (32.3)	3.29	0.53	A
Immersive Entertainment and Recreation	39 (24.7)	78 (49.4)	37 (23.4)	4 (2.5)	2.04	0.77	D
Overall Mean					2.86	0.62	A

Key: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree, SD* Standard Deviation, Des.- Decision

Tables 3 explored respondents' perceptions of current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems tailored to individuals with diverse disabilities and significant difference in perceptions of current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems across the status of respondents. Table 3 shows that respondents strongly agreed with the use of VR systems for rehabilitation and physical therapy (mean = 3.61) and agreed with its applications for accessibility for visual disabilities (mean = 3.21), integration of AI for personalization (mean = 3.09), and enhanced educational and vocational training (mean = 3.29). However, respondents disagreed with the use of VR systems for cognitive and social skill development (mean = 1.93) and immersive entertainment and recreation (mean = 2.04). The overall mean score of 2.86 suggests general agreement with the listed VR advancements and innovations.

HO₁: There is a significant difference in perceptions of current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems across statuses of the respondents

Table 4: One-Way ANOVA Results on the significant difference in perceptions of current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems across statuses

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.024	2	.012	.186	.831
Within Groups	10.174	155	.066		
Total	10.199	157			

The ANOVA results (Table 4) indicate no significant differences in perceptions across the statuses of respondents ($F = 0.186, p > 0.05$). This implies consistent views among respondent groups regarding VR system advancements.

Research Question 3: What ways could virtual reality technologies help overcome accessibility barriers faced by individuals with disabilities?

Table 5: Respondents' Perceptions of VR in Overcoming Accessibility Barriers

Items Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SD*	Des.
Mobility and Physical Accessibility	3 (1.9)	7 (4.4)	52 (32.9)	96 (60.8)	3.53	0.67	SA
Sensory Accessibility	61 (38.6)	82 (51.9)	12 (7.6)	3 (1.9)	1.73	0.68	D

Cognitive Accessibility	2 (1.3)	7 (4.4)	32 (20.3)	117 (74.1)	3.67	0.62	SA
Workplace Inclusivity	3 (1.9)	8 (5.1)	40 (25.3)	107 (67.7)	3.59	0.68	SA
Healthcare and Rehabilitation	0 (0.0)	10 (6.3)	51 (32.3)	97 (61.4)	3.55	0.61	SA
Overall Mean					3.21	0.65	A

Key: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree, SD* Standard Deviation, Des.- Decision

Table 5 examined respondents' perceptions of how virtual reality (VR) technologies can address accessibility barriers for individuals with disabilities. The table shows that respondents strongly agreed with the role of VR technologies in enhancing mobility and physical accessibility (mean = 3.53), cognitive accessibility (mean = 3.67), workplace inclusivity (mean = 3.59), and healthcare and rehabilitation (mean = 3.55). These findings suggest that VR is perceived as a significant tool for overcoming various accessibility barriers. However, respondents disagreed with the statement regarding sensory accessibility, reflected by a lower mean score of 1.73. The overall mean score of 3.21 indicates that respondents generally agree on the potential of VR technologies to address accessibility barriers faced by individuals with disabilities. The results highlight the transformative potential of VR in key areas, though some barriers, such as sensory accessibility, may require further advancements and innovation.

Research Question 4: What are the challenges that limit the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool for individuals with disability?

Table 6: Respondents' Perceptions of Challenges Limiting VR Adoption

Items Statement	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	SD*	Des.
Technical barriers	0 (0.0)	6 (3.8)	37 (23.4)	115 (72.8)	3.69	0.54	SA
Economic constraints	3 (1.9)	17 (10.8)	91 (57.6)	47 (29.7)	3.15	0.68	A
Design and usability challenges	6 (3.8)	12 (7.6)	32 (20.3)	108 (68.4)	3.53	0.80	SA
Lack of awareness and Regulatory Issues	7 (4.4)	12 (7.6)	34 (21.5)	105 (66.5)	3.50	0.82	SA
Insufficient Standards	10 (6.3)	12 (7.6)	89 (56.3)	47 (29.7)	3.09	0.79	A
Overall Mean					3.39	0.72	A

Key: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree, SD* Standard Deviation, Des.- Decision

Tables 6 present respondents' perceptions of the challenges limiting the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool for individuals with disabilities and significant difference in perceptions of challenges limiting the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool across the status of respondents. Table 6 shows that respondents strongly agreed with challenges related to technical barriers (mean = 3.69), design and usability challenges (mean = 3.53), and lack of awareness and regulatory issues (mean = 3.50). These challenges were identified as significant limitations to VR adoption. Respondents agreed on the challenges posed by economic constraints (mean = 3.15) and insufficient standards (mean = 3.09). The overall mean score of 3.39 suggests that respondents generally agree that these challenges limit the adoption of VR technologies as an accessibility tool.

HO₂: There is a significant difference in perceptions of challenges limiting the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool across statuses of the respondents

Table 7: One-Way ANOVA Results on the significant difference in perceptions of challenges limiting the adoption of VR as an accessibility tool across statuses

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.164	2	.082	.990	.374
Within Groups	12.830	155	.083		
Total	12.994	157			

The ANOVA results (Table 7) indicate no significant differences in perceptions across the statuses of respondents ($F = 0.990, p > 0.05$). This suggests that the challenges are perceived similarly among the different respondent groups.

Discussion of Findings

Results in table 1, shows the demographic characteristics of this study, comprising the status, gender and age distribution. This shows the percentage and frequency of status in categories: school librarians/senior workers, individual with disability and technology specialist. The gender covers, male and the female, include the percentages of the respondent. Their ages were distributed accordingly. Table 2 above shows that the respondents, agreed that there are different categories of disability, which ranges from intellectual disability to Austin Spectrum Disorder, while some respondents disagreed on some disabilities, such as Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, Cerebral Palsy and Gait Disorders.

This could be that they don't actually know much about such intellectual disability. This suggestion of Hickman (2023) opined that each disabilities has categories, such as developmental delays in children up to age nine, or the combined difficulties of deaf-blindness requiring unique interventions and attention. These classifications ensure tailored educational plans and accommodations to support individuals effectively, as he has been meeting the lifetime legal needs of children and adults with disabilities, the elderly, and their families. The result in table 3 shows the respondent perception of current advancement in VR system for individuals with diverse disabilities. There is a significant difference in perceptions on current innovations in VR across the respondents. The respondents strongly agreed with the use of VR for rehabilitation, also its application for accessibility for visual disabilities to enhance educational and vocational training. This is in line with what Dartmouth, (2023) explained that this could include personalised therapy plans, integrating real-time data analytics to optimise rehabilitation routines based on user progress and engagement. However, some respondents also said that with dependency in the use of VR system for cognitive and social skills development is paramount which is supported by Deluca, et al (2025), who also inferred that Virtual reality environments are being customised to support individuals with cognitive impairments, offering secure settings where they can practice memory recall, improve social interactions, and manage everyday tasks. Hypothesis findings in table 4 result no significance difference, with value= ($F = 0.186, p > 0.05$). This implies consistent views among respondent groups regarding VR system advancements. Table 5 shows how VR technologies assist to overcome accessibility barriers for individual with disabilities. Some respondents strongly agreed with such role of VR technologies for enhancement of mobility and physical accessibility barriers for the benefits of disability individuals. The results show emphasis in the transformative potentials of VR as a key for disability. This was supported by the findings of Catania, et al. (2025) inferred that Virtual Reality (VR) is a transformative technology that has garnered increasing attention in the field of neuroscience, neuropsychology, and cognitive rehabilitation, by immersing individuals in interactive, multisensory environments. Results in table 6, show that all the challenges examined are the limiting factors to the adoption of VR as an accessibility tools, most especially the technical barriers, design & usability challenges and lack of awareness and regulatory issues. All these are seen as significant limitations to VR adoption, which hinders individual disabilities. Yang (2024) opined that many VR systems are not designed to integrate with existing accessibility aids, such as screen readers or adaptive switches, further alienating potential users with sensory or

motor impairments. Hypothesis in table 7 shows no significance differences in perceptions across the statuses of respondents, with value = (F = 0.990, p > 0.05). This suggests that the challenges are perceived similarly among the different respondent groups.

Conclusion

Advancements in AI, sensory integration, and user personalization, is of vital importance to individual with disability. The rapid evolution of VR systems offers transformative possibilities for individuals with diverse impairments, addressing barriers in rehabilitation, education, and daily life. VR holds the potential to become an essential tool for fostering inclusivity and improving quality of life. VR's ability to simulate, adapt, and enhance real-world experiences makes it a transformative tool for breaking down accessibility barriers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are deduced from the study.

1. There should be development of adaptive technologies like eye-tracking and voice controls to replace traditional controllers, advocacy for insurance coverage, and the establishment of industry-wide accessibility standards.
2. There should be user-centered design practices that involve individuals with disabilities in the development process.
3. There should be VR technologies for enhancement of mobility and physical accessibility barriers for the benefits of disability individuals.
4. There should be current advancements and potential innovations in VR systems for individuals with diverse disabilities.

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